

Plectranthus saccatus Stoep jacaranda

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Group: Eudicot

Size: 0.5 to 2 meters in height

Distribution:

Plectranthus saccatus is found naturally in the Eastern Cape and KwaZulu-Natal in forest habitats, usually in moist, rocky, semi shaded habitats.

Importance:

This species is cultivated locally and internationally as a flowering ornamental. Compared with other members of the genus it has relatively large flowers and is easy to propagate. It has also been used in the development of several South African commercial hybrids, including 'Mona Lavender', bred at Kirstenbosch, and the Cape Angels series.

PromethION Sequencing Report:

Output: 19.46 Gigabases

Approximate N50: 18.49 kilobases

Draft Genome Assembly Statistics:

Assembler used: Hifiasm

Genome Length: 0.5 Gigabases

BUSCO completeness score: 99.1% [Single: 78.4%, Duplicated: 20.7%]

BUSCO database: viridiplantae

Assembly N50: 7 423.36 kilobases

Contig number: 393

Sample Contributor contact details:

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